

RapidCNE: A High-Throughput GPU Library for Comprehensive Cluster Number Estimation

Yang Yang^[0000–0001–8190–8683] and Edward Curry^[0000–0001–8236–6433]

Insight Centre for Data Analytics, Data Science Institute,
University of Galway, Ireland
yang.yang@insight-centre.org, edward.curry@universityofgalway.ie

Abstract. Estimating the number of clusters (k) is a central but computationally demanding step in unsupervised learning. Practitioners typically sweep over a range of candidate k values and evaluate multiple cluster validity indices (CVIs), which quickly becomes a bottleneck for large datasets. Existing CVI implementations are scattered across libraries, expose heterogeneous APIs, and are almost exclusively CPU-bound, making comprehensive evaluation impractical in interactive workflows. We introduce **RapidCNE**, a comprehensive, open-source library for high-throughput cluster number estimation on GPUs. RapidCNE provides GPU-native implementations of several popular CVIs and is built around a *compute-once, use-many* engine that performs a single KMeans sweep on the GPU, caches labels, centroids, and inertia, and then evaluates multiple indices with minimal redundant computation. Across 11 real-world datasets, RapidCNE achieves substantial speedups over CPU baselines, reducing total runtime by roughly a factor of five on average and up to 14× on individual datasets, while enabling the simultaneous evaluation of five indices. Our accuracy study further characterizes the behavior of different CVIs and highlights the importance of multi-index consensus for robust cluster number estimation. Code is available at ¹.

Keywords: Cluster Number Estimation · GPU Acceleration · KMeans · High-Performance Clustering · Unsupervised Learning

1 Introduction

Estimating the number of clusters k is a foundational and often challenging problem in unsupervised learning [13]. An inappropriate choice of k can invalidate downstream analysis, leading to misleading interpretation of the underlying structure. A standard approach is to use *cluster validity indices* (CVIs) that quantify the quality of a clustering for a given k , and then select the value of k that optimizes the chosen index.

In practice, this procedure is expensive. For each candidate k in a user-defined range, a clustering algorithm such as KMeans must be executed, and one or more CVI scores must be computed. For large datasets or wide search

¹ Codes available at <https://github.com/Yang233666/RapidCNE>

ranges, this iterative process becomes a major computational bottleneck and often forces practitioners to compromise, for example by using a single index or a coarse search grid.

The situation is exacerbated by the fragmented ecosystem of CVI implementations. Although many indices have been proposed in the literature, they are spread across different CPU-based libraries (for example scikit-learn and SciPy) and expose inconsistent APIs. As a result, data scientists face an undesirable trade-off: either run a superficial CNE analysis with a single metric, or accept prohibitive runtimes that are incompatible with interactive data exploration. This suggests that cluster number estimation (CNE) should be treated as a first-class high-performance computing problem.

This paper addresses this gap with **RapidCNE**, a comprehensive, GPU-accelerated library for cluster number estimation. RapidCNE is designed around a principled *algorithm-system co-design* that rethinks the CNE workflow for modern parallel hardware. Our contributions are fourfold:

1. **Unified high-performance CNE library.** We present, to the best of our knowledge, the first dedicated CNE library that offers GPU-native implementations of widely used indices, including Calinski–Harabasz [3], Xie–Beni [18], Davies–Bouldin [5], and a GPU-friendly Elbow [11] and Log-Jump [12] implementation, all under a single, user-friendly API.
2. **Compute-once, use-many architecture.** We introduce a caching engine that performs the expensive KMeans sweep across all candidate k values once on the GPU. The resulting labels, centroids, and inertias are cached in device memory and reused across indices, eliminating repeated clustering and redundant distance computations.
3. **Rigorous empirical evaluation.** We benchmark RapidCNE on 11 real-world datasets, comparing GPU and CPU backends in terms of wall-clock time and per-index runtime. In addition, we systematically evaluate the accuracy of five CVIs and analyze their biases and failure modes.
4. **Open-source tool for the community.** RapidCNE is provided as an open-source library intended to make robust, multi-index CNE a practical and interactive step in modern data science workflows, and to support reproducible evaluation of CNE strategies.

2 Related Work

Our work connects classic clustering methodology, cluster validity indices, and high-performance GPU computing.

2.1 Clustering Methods

Clustering is a fundamental tool for exploratory data analysis and has been studied extensively in unsupervised learning. Classical approaches include KMeans [7], hierarchical clustering [9], Gaussian mixture models [2], and spectral clustering [15]. These methods have been deployed in diverse domains such as natural

language processing [16,1], knowledge graphs [19,20,21], and computer vision [4,8].

More recently, deep clustering methods [17] integrate representation learning with clustering objectives, seeking embeddings that are directly optimized for cluster structure. Despite this progress, estimating the appropriate number of clusters (for example, k in KMeans) remains a difficult model selection problem for both traditional and deep clustering methods.

2.2 Cluster Validity Indices (CVIs)

The cluster validity literature is extensive. CVIs can be broadly grouped into internal indices, which evaluate cluster structure using only the data and the partition, and external indices, which compare the partition to external labels. This work focuses on internal indices that do not require ground truth.

Internal indices often balance measures of compactness (intra-cluster variance) and separation (inter-cluster distance). The Calinski–Harabasz (CH) index [3] uses a ratio of between-cluster to within-cluster sums of squares. The Davies–Bouldin (DB) index [5] penalizes clusterings where clusters are close and internally dispersed by minimizing the average similarity between each cluster and its most similar neighbour. The Xie–Beni (XB) index [18] measures the ratio between the total intra-cluster variance and the squared distance between the closest pair of cluster centers. More recent heuristics, such as the Log-Jump method [12], introduce information-theoretic perspectives on selecting k , and related ideas have also been adapted to determine training data size for link prediction calibration [22].

Although these indices are widely used, their computational cost grows with the number of samples, dimensionality, and candidate k values. Existing implementations typically recompute distances or clustering results repeatedly, which becomes prohibitive for comprehensive CNE across multiple indices and a wide range of k .

2.3 High-Performance and GPU-Accelerated Clustering

The adoption of general-purpose GPU computing has substantially accelerated many classical machine learning algorithms. RAPIDS cuML [10] provides GPU-accelerated implementations of several standard algorithms, including a highly optimized KMeans routine that we leverage in RapidCNE. Faiss [6] focuses on billion-scale similarity search and clustering for very large datasets.

However, these frameworks primarily accelerate clustering for a single, user-chosen value of k . They do not offer an end-to-end solution for cluster number estimation, which requires sweeping across many candidate k values and evaluating multiple CVIs. To the best of our knowledge, RapidCNE is the first library explicitly designed and optimized for the complete CNE workflow on GPUs, from KMeans sweeps to multi-index evaluation.

Fig. 1. The RapidCNE Architecture.

3 The RapidCNE Library Architecture

RapidCNE is designed as a high-performance bridge between theoretical cluster analysis and modern hardware. The library centers on a modular `Cluster Estimator` class that follows the scikit-learn estimator API while encapsulating GPU memory management and backend selection. The architecture is guided by three principles: dynamic backend selection, minimal host-device data transfer, and fully vectorized index computation.

3.1 Dynamic Backend Dispatch

To ensure broad applicability, RapidCNE implements a unified facade that abstracts over the underlying numerical backend. Upon initialization, the library checks for CUDA-enabled hardware and the availability of `cupy` and `cuml`:

- **GPU mode.** When a compatible GPU is detected, `cupy` serves as the numerical backend and `cuml.cluster.KMeans` is used as the clustering operator. Data are transferred once into GPU memory and kept resident for the duration of the analysis.
- **CPU fallback.** In the absence of a suitable GPU, RapidCNE seamlessly falls back to `numpy` and `sklearn.cluster.KMeans`, preserving the same public API.

This dynamic dispatch allows users to write a single analysis pipeline that scales from a laptop to a server GPU without code changes.

3.2 The KMeansSweep Engine: Compute Once, Use Many

The main computational cost in CNE comes from repeatedly executing clustering across a range of k values. Naive implementations often recompute cluster assignments or distance matrices for each CVI, resulting in substantial redundant work.

RapidCNE addresses this with the `KMeansSweep` engine. During fitting, the engine performs a sweep over the candidate range $k \in [k_{\min}, k_{\max}]$. For each k , it runs `KMeans` once and records:

- the cluster labels for each point,
- the cluster centroids,
- the inertia (sum of squared distances to the assigned centroid).

In GPU mode, these outputs are kept in device memory (using `output_type = 'copy'` in cuML) and stored in a lookup structure keyed by k . This design decouples the expensive optimization step (finding centroids) from the CVI evaluation step and ensures that each k is clustered at most once. All supported indices (Elbow, Log-Jump, CH, DB, XB) are reformulated to depend only on these cached primitives and the original data matrix.

3.3 Vectorized CVI Reformulation

To exploit the Single Instruction, Multiple Threads (SIMT) nature of GPUs, RapidCNE avoids Python-level loops in the CVI implementations. Instead, indices are computed via broadcasted vector and matrix operations:

1. **Calinski–Harabasz.** Inter-cluster dispersion and intra-cluster dispersion are computed from cached centroids and labels using matrix multiplications and reductions that map naturally to cuBLAS primitives.
2. **Davies–Bouldin.** Rather than iterating over all pairs of clusters (i, j) , we compute all pairwise centroid distances in a single operation and combine them with vectorized estimates of cluster scatter to obtain the similarity ratios for all cluster pairs at once.
3. **Xie–Beni.** The numerator (sum of squared distances to the assigned centroid) is derived from inertia, while the denominator (squared minimum distance between centroids) comes from a vectorized centroid self-distance matrix of size $K \times K$. This avoids looping over the data dimension.

By structuring each index as a small number of dense tensor operations, RapidCNE maintains high GPU occupancy and minimizes kernel launch overhead. This yields significant speedups while preserving numerical equivalence to standard definitions.

4 Experimental Evaluation

We now evaluate RapidCNE along two dimensions: (1) accuracy of different CVIs in recovering the true number of clusters, and (2) computational efficiency of the GPU implementation relative to a CPU baseline.

4.1 Evaluation Protocol

Our evaluation protocol is designed to reflect realistic usage in exploratory data analysis and model selection.

Table 1. Statistics of the 11 benchmark datasets used in our evaluation. The datasets vary in size, dimensionality, and number of clusters, providing a robust testbed for CNE methods.

Dataset	Samples (N)	Features (p)	True Clusters (k)
Echocardiogram	61	9	2
Iris	150	4	3
Seeds	210	7	3
Wine	178	13	3
Colon Cancer	62	2000	2
Prostate Cancer	102	6033	2
Mice Protein	552	77	8
Abalone	4177	8	28
CNAE-9	1080	856	9
Vowel	990	13	11
Synthetic Control	600	60	6

- **Accuracy.** We examine five CNE methods: Log-Jump [12], Elbow [11], Calinski–Harabasz (CH) [3], Davies–Bouldin (DB) [5], and Xie–Beni (XB) [18]. For each dataset, each method predicts a cluster number k_{pred} from a predefined search range. We report the relative error $\text{RE} = |k_{\text{pred}} - k_{\text{true}}|/k_{\text{true}}$ and the average relative error (ARE) across all datasets.
- **Efficiency.** We measure the wall-clock time required to compute all five indices over the search range of k . We compare the **CPU** backend (using scikit-learn and NumPy) to the **GPU** backend (using cuML and Rapid-CNE’s vectorized kernels), and we also report the time attributed to each index.

For all experiments, KMeans hyperparameters (initialization, maximum iterations, and tolerance) are held fixed across CPU and GPU runs to ensure a fair comparison.

4.2 Datasets

To obtain a diverse and challenging benchmark, we select 11 publicly available datasets from OpenML [14] that span a wide range of properties:

- **Sample size (N).** From small datasets such as *Echocardiogram* ($N = 61$) to larger ones such as *Abalone* ($N = 4177$).
- **Dimensionality (p).** From low-dimensional datasets such as *Iris* ($p = 4$) to high-dimensional bioinformatics datasets such as *Prostate Cancer* ($p = 6033$).
- **Number of clusters (k).** From binary clustering problems (for example, cancer datasets with $k = 2$) to multi-class scenarios such as *Abalone* ($k = 28$) and *Vowel* ($k = 11$).

Table 2. Accuracy comparison: predicted clusters (k_{pred}) and relative error (RE) for each CNE method. The average relative error (ARE) over all datasets is given in the last row. Lower ARE is better.

Dataset	Log-Jump			Elbow		Calinski-Harabasz		Davies-Bouldin		Xie-Beni	
	True k	k_{pred}	RE								
Echocardiogram	2	6	2.000	3	0.500	2	0.000	2	0.000	2	0.000
Iris	3	9	2.000	4	0.333	3	0.000	2	0.333	2	0.333
Seeds	3	14	3.667	5	0.667	3	0.000	2	0.333	2	0.333
Wine	3	13	3.333	5	0.667	13	3.333	7	1.333	2	0.333
Colon Cancer	2	6	2.000	4	1.000	2	0.000	7	2.500	7	2.500
Prostate Cancer	2	9	3.500	4	1.000	2	0.000	2	0.000	2	0.000
Mice Protein	8	23	1.875	8	0.000	2	0.750	22	1.750	22	1.750
Abalone	28	61	1.179	10	0.643	22	0.214	2	0.929	8	0.714
CNAE-9	9	31	2.444	12	0.333	2	0.778	30	2.333	27	2.000
Vowel	11	25	1.273	9	0.182	2	0.818	2	0.818	2	0.818
Synthetic Ctrl.	6	21	2.500	8	0.333	3	0.500	2	0.667	2	0.667
Overall ARE			2.343		0.514		0.581		1.000		0.859

- **Domain diversity.** The datasets cover application areas including medicine (*Echocardiogram*, *Cancer*), biology (*Mice Protein*), agriculture (*Seeds*), and time series (*Synthetic Control*), supporting conclusions that generalize across domains.

Table 1 summarizes the key statistics of all datasets. All experiments are run on an NVIDIA A40 GPU and an Intel Xeon Gold 6248R CPU.

5 Results and Discussion

Our experiments address two questions: (1) how different CNE criteria behave in terms of accuracy across heterogeneous datasets, and (2) how much computational benefit RapidCNE provides when computing multiple indices jointly on the GPU.

5.1 Accuracy Analysis: No Single Winner, but Clear Patterns

Table 2 reports the predicted cluster number and relative error (RE) for all five criteria, together with the average relative error (ARE) across the eleven datasets. The results confirm that CNE is intrinsically difficult and that no single index is uniformly reliable, but several useful patterns emerge.

Elbow and Calinski–Harabasz as strong general-purpose choices. Among the five methods, the Elbow criterion and the Calinski–Harabasz (CH) index obtain the lowest average errors, with ARE 0.514 and 0.581, respectively. CH is often exact on classic, well-separated datasets such as *Echocardiogram*, *Iris*, *Seeds*, *Colon Cancer*, and *Prostate Cancer*, where it recovers the true number of clusters (RE = 0). Elbow tends to be conservative but consistently close to the ground truth

across many datasets (for example, *Vowel*: $k_{\text{pred}} = 9$ vs. $k_{\text{true}} = 11$, RE = 0.182; *CNAE-9*: RE = 0.333; *Abalone*: RE = 0.643).

This suggests a useful division of roles: CH can be highly accurate when its assumptions hold, while Elbow behaves as a more stable, middle-of-the-road estimator with fewer extreme failures.

Systematic biases of Davies–Bouldin and Xie–Beni. The Davies–Bouldin (DB) and Xie–Beni (XB) indices exhibit intermediate performance, with ARE 1.000 and 0.859, respectively. DB frequently underestimates k , collapsing to $k = 2$ on several multi-class datasets (*Iris*, *Seeds*, *Abalone*, *Vowel*, *Synthetic Control*), which reflects its preference for a small number of compact, well-separated clusters. XB shows similar underestimation behavior on some datasets but also overshoots dramatically on others (for example, *CNAE-9* with $k_{\text{pred}} = 27$, RE = 2.000).

These patterns support using DB and XB as complementary diagnostics rather than primary decision-makers, for instance to test whether a dataset is better summarized by fewer, more compact clusters.

Value of multi-index consensus. Across datasets, different indices are correct or near-correct on different problems. On *Mice Protein*, for example, Elbow exactly recovers $k = 8$, whereas CH underestimates and DB/XB overestimate; on *Vowel*, only Elbow is close to the true k . This diversity motivates RapidCNE’s design: by making it inexpensive to compute several indices simultaneously, users can exploit agreement between indices (or highlight disagreements) instead of relying on a single, brittle criterion. In practice, combining Elbow and CH with domain knowledge already yields more robust choices of k than any individual index alone.

5.2 Performance Analysis: High-Throughput CNE on the GPU

Table 3 summarizes the wall-clock time for the CPU and GPU implementations, including the time attributed to each index. The results reveal three regimes driven by dataset size and dimensionality.

Small datasets: overhead dominates. On small tabular datasets such as *Echocardiogram*, *Iris*, *Seeds*, and *Wine*, the CPU backend is slightly faster (for example, *Echocardiogram*: 0.59 s on CPU vs. 0.87 s on GPU; *Iris*: 0.73 s vs. 1.11 s). This is expected: for small N , the cost of initializing the GPU context, allocating memory, and launching kernels outweighs the benefit of parallelism. RapidCNE exposes both backends so that users can select the CPU implementation for such small-scale exploratory analyses.

Medium to large datasets: strong GPU speedups. For medium and large datasets, GPU acceleration yields substantial speedups:

- **Mice Protein:** runtime drops from 62.1 s (CPU) to 5.1 s (GPU), a speedup of about $12\times$.

Table 3. Performance of RapidCNE (CPU vs. GPU). We report total wall-clock time and the execution times (in seconds) attributed to each method, for both backends.

Dataset	Total Time		Execution Time per Method (s)									
	(s)		Log-Jump		Elbow		Calinski-Harabasz		Davies-Bouldin		Xie-Beni	
	CPU	GPU	CPU	GPU	CPU	GPU	CPU	GPU	CPU	GPU	CPU	GPU
Echocardiogram	0.591	0.869	0.118	0.156	0.118	0.162	0.118	0.207	0.119	0.177	0.118	0.167
Iris	0.730	1.112	0.145	0.210	0.146	0.211	0.146	0.223	0.147	0.246	0.146	0.222
Seeds	1.078	1.592	0.215	0.304	0.215	0.304	0.215	0.316	0.217	0.350	0.216	0.318
Wine	0.828	1.305	0.165	0.248	0.165	0.249	0.165	0.260	0.167	0.287	0.166	0.261
Colon Cancer	0.888	3.484	0.175	0.690	0.175	0.691	0.176	0.697	0.183	0.707	0.179	0.699
Prostate Cancer	17.417	17.368	3.462	3.470	3.461	3.462	3.462	3.470	3.526	3.495	3.507	3.480
Mice Protein	62.099	5.137	12.414	1.016	12.413	0.992	12.414	1.016	12.431	1.114	12.428	1.024
Abalone	50.504	25.972	10.079	5.046	10.073	4.980	10.079	5.046	10.151	5.815	10.128	5.152
CNAE-9	202.073	32.399	40.157	6.431	40.155	6.398	40.157	6.431	40.805	6.653	40.801	6.520
Vowel	96.876	6.764	19.371	1.329	19.369	1.299	19.371	1.329	19.391	1.499	19.376	1.339
Synthetic Ctrl.	65.154	4.727	13.027	0.930	13.026	0.906	13.027	0.930	13.040	1.045	13.035	0.941
Total (all datasets)	498.238	100.729	99.330	19.925	99.316	19.654	99.330	19.925	100.177	21.388	100.100	20.123

- **Vowel:** runtime decreases from 96.9 s to 6.8 s, the largest observed speedup of about 14.3 \times .
- **CNAE-9:** the CPU requires 202.1 s, whereas the GPU completes in 32.4 s (about 6.2 \times faster).
- **Synthetic Control:** runtime reduces from 65.2 s to 4.7 s, a speedup of about 13.8 \times .

Even on a moderately sized dataset such as *Abalone*, the GPU nearly halves the total runtime (50.5 s vs. 26.0 s). Summed over all datasets, the total CPU time is 498.2 s compared to 100.7 s on the GPU, corresponding to an overall throughput improvement of roughly a factor of five while computing all five indices.

The per-index breakdown shows that all CVIs benefit similarly from GPU acceleration: Log-Jump, Elbow, CH, DB, and XB each see comparable reductions, indicating that the underlying kernels are balanced and do not favour any particular index.

High-dimensional, low-sample regime. The *Prostate Cancer* dataset illustrates a different regime: very few samples ($N = 102$) but extremely high dimensionality ($p = 6033$). Here, CPU and GPU times are nearly identical (around 17.4 s) for both backends. This suggests that memory bandwidth and data movement dominate the cost and that neither architecture offers a clear advantage in this “wide” setting. In such cases, the choice of backend can be guided by practical considerations such as hardware availability or integration with other GPU workloads.

Practical implications. Overall, RapidCNE turns comprehensive cluster number estimation into a largely interactive operation for medium and large datasets. Analyses that previously required minutes on a CPU (for example, *Mice Protein*, *Vowel*, *CNAE-9*) can now be executed in a few seconds on a single GPU, making it feasible to:

- iterate quickly over feature subsets or preprocessing choices,
- compare multiple CVIs on the fly and inspect their consensus,
- embed CNE within larger pipelines such as AutoML or hyperparameter search without dominating runtime.

The accuracy results underscore the importance of multi-index consensus for robust CNE, while the performance results show that RapidCNE’s GPU backend makes such comprehensive evaluation practical at scale.

6 Conclusion and Future Work

The computational cost of cluster number estimation has long limited the use of multiple indices and wide search ranges in practical workflows. This paper introduced **RapidCNE**, a GPU-accelerated library that treats CNE as a high-throughput computing task. By re-engineering a set of popular CVIs around a *compute-once, use-many* architecture and vectorized GPU kernels, RapidCNE makes comprehensive, multi-index evaluation efficient and practical.

Our experiments on 11 real-world datasets show that RapidCNE reduces total runtime by about a factor of five over a CPU baseline, with per-dataset speedups of up to 14×, while supporting simultaneous evaluation of five indices. The accuracy study further highlights that no single CVI is universally reliable and that Elbow and Calinski–Harabasz perform best on average, while DB/XB exhibit systematic biases. These findings reinforce the value of RapidCNE’s multi-index design.

In future work, we plan to extend RapidCNE in several directions. First, we aim to support additional clustering algorithms beyond KMeans, such as hierarchical clustering and density-based methods like DBSCAN. Second, we intend to incorporate more recent CVIs from the literature and explore meta-strategies for combining indices. Finally, we will carry out a detailed comparison against optimized multi-core CPU implementations to quantify performance gains across a wider range of hardware configurations.

Acknowledgments

This publication has emanated from research conducted with the financial support of Taighde Éireann – Research Ireland under Grant number SFI/12/RC/2289 P2.

References

1. Baker, L.D., McCallum, A.K.: Distributional clustering of words for text classification. In: Proceedings of the 21st annual international ACM SIGIR conference on Research and development in information retrieval. pp. 96–103 (1998)
2. Bishop, C.M., Nasrabadi, N.M.: Pattern recognition and machine learning, vol. 4. Springer (2006)

3. Caliński, T., Harabasz, J.: A dendrite method for cluster analysis. *Communications in Statistics-theory and Methods* **3**(1), 1–27 (1974)
4. Coleman, G.B., Andrews, H.C.: Image segmentation by clustering. *Proceedings of the IEEE* **67**(5), 773–785 (1979)
5. Davies, D.L., Bouldin, D.W.: A cluster separation measure. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence* (2), 224–227 (2009)
6. Johnson, J., Douze, M., Jégou, H.: Billion-scale similarity search with gpus. *IEEE Transactions on Big Data* **7**(3), 535–547 (2019)
7. McQueen, J.B.: Some methods of classification and analysis of multivariate observations. In: *Proc. of 5th Berkeley Symposium on Math. Stat. and Prob.* pp. 281–297 (1967)
8. Minaee, S., Boykov, Y., Porikli, F., Plaza, A., Kehtarnavaz, N., Terzopoulos, D.: Image segmentation using deep learning: A survey. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence* **44**(7), 3523–3542 (2021)
9. Murtagh, F., Contreras, P.: Algorithms for hierarchical clustering: an overview. *Wiley interdisciplinary reviews: data mining and knowledge discovery* **2**(1), 86–97 (2012)
10. RAPIDS Development Team: Rapids: Open gpu data science. <https://rapids.ai/> (2023), accessed: October 6, 2025
11. Salvador, S., Chan, P.: Determining the number of clusters/segments in hierarchical clustering/segmentation algorithms. In: *16th IEEE international conference on tools with artificial intelligence.* pp. 576–584. IEEE (2004)
12. Shen, W., Yang, Y., Liu, Y.: Multi-view clustering for open knowledge base canonicalization. In: *SIGKDD.* pp. 1578–1588 (2022)
13. Tibshirani, R., Walther, G., Hastie, T.: Estimating the number of clusters in a data set via the gap statistic. *Journal of the royal statistical society: series b (statistical methodology)* **63**(2), 411–423 (2001)
14. Vanschoren, J., Van Rijn, J.N., Bischl, B., Torgo, L.: Openml: networked science in machine learning. *ACM SIGKDD Explorations Newsletter* **15**(2), 49–60 (2014)
15. Von Luxburg, U.: A tutorial on spectral clustering. *Statistics and computing* **17**(4), 395–416 (2007)
16. Willett, P.: Recent trends in hierarchic document clustering: a critical review. *Information processing & management* **24**(5), 577–597 (1988)
17. Xie, J., Girshick, R., Farhadi, A.: Unsupervised deep embedding for clustering analysis. In: *International conference on machine learning.* pp. 478–487. PMLR (2016)
18. Xie, X.L., Beni, G.: A validity measure for fuzzy clustering. *IEEE Transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence* **13**(8), 841–847 (2002)
19. Yang, Y., Curry, E.: Open knowledge base canonicalization: Techniques and challenges. In: *Text2KG@ESWC* (2024)
20. Yang, Y., Curry, E.: Neuro-symbolic techniques in open knowledge graph canonicalization. In: *Handbook on Neurosymbolic AI and Knowledge Graphs,* pp. 280–299. IOS Press (2025)
21. Yang, Y., Shen, W., Shu, J., Liu, Y., Curry, E., Li, G.: Cmvc+: a multi-view clustering framework for open knowledge base canonicalization via contrastive learning. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering* (2025)
22. Yang, Y., Timilsina, M., Curry, E.: Kge calibrator: An efficient probability calibration method of knowledge graph embedding models for trustworthy link prediction. In: *Proceedings of the 2025 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing.* pp. 29952–29975 (2025)